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A STUDY ON TEACHING COMPETENCY OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

Sijila Das.M.K^{*1}, Mrs. Nalinilatha.M²

^{*1} MEd Scholar, RVS College of Education, India

²Assistant Professor in Tamil Education, RVS College of Education, India

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Abstract

The role of teacher is proficient, be composed of academic, didactic and social roles. Academic roles cover teaching, instructing and supervisory characters and pedagogical characters include instructional, valuation and simplifying roles. The study aimed to identify the teaching competency of secondary school teachers. The investigator adopted survey method to study the teaching competency between teachers from selected government, private and aided school. For this study a sample of 300 school teachers from eight various schools which are situated in Palakkad district selected by the investigator using simple random sampling technique. The findings revealed that there is no significant difference towards teaching competency among selected secondary school teachers with respect to personal variables like Gender, Marital Status, Educational Qualification, Type of Management and Teaching experience. The findings of the study help to discover the teaching competency of secondary school teachers in the society.

Keywords: Teaching Competency; Education; Teachers.

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1. Introduction

Teachers are the mainstay of the complete education system. Their efficiency and proficiencies the foundation on which the organisation of quality in any society is made. Competence is a model used to describe the skills of a single assimilated through learning and education. An educator executes number of instructional and associated activities inside and outside the classroom. These activities are of varied types. The operative organization of these activities would have need of that a teacher holds a certain amount of knowledge and also certain attitudes and talents. This is known as teaching competence. In other difference of opinion, teacher competence refers to “the accurate way of carrying units of knowledge, application and talents to

students”. Therefore, an attempt has been made by the investigator to study the teaching competence of secondary school teachers.

1.1. Objectives of the Study

There are two main types of objectives undertaken by the investigator in this study work.

1.1.1. General Objectives

To study on teaching competency among selected secondary school teachers in Palakkad district
 To adopt questionnaire on teaching competency scale among secondary school teachers.

1.1.2. Specific Objectives

To find out the teaching competency among secondary school teachers.
 To find out the impact of personal variables like Gender, Marital Status, Educational Qualification, Type of Management and Teaching Experience on teaching competency among secondary school teachers.

2. Research Design

The investigator adopted survey method to study the teaching competency among secondary school teachers. For the study about teaching competency, the sample size taken is 300 secondary school teachers from 8 various schools which are situated in and around Palakkad district in Kerala.

Table 1: Distribution of Samples based on Variables

S.NO	Category	Subgroups	Number	%	Total
1.	Gender	Male	139	46.3%	300
		Female	161	53.7%	
2.	Marital Status	Married	163	54.3%	300
		Unmarried	137	45.7%	
3.	Educational Qualification	PG	110	36.7%	300
		UG	190	63.3%	
4.	Type of Management	Govt.	98	32.7%	300
		Aided	111	37%	
		Private	91	30.3%	
5.	Teaching Experience	0-5 years	99	33%	300
		5- 10 years	129	43%	
		Above 10 years	72	24%	

Table 2: Scoring of Each item

S.No	Dimension	Question no.	Scoring				
			SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	Teaching Competency Scale	1 to 35	5	4	3	2	1

Table 3: Ranks assigned for the Teaching Competency Scale

Teaching Competency Scale	
Scores	Rank
35 to 81	Low
82 to 127	Moderate
128 to 175	High

HYPOTHESIS 1:

There will be a significant mean score difference towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to Gender

Table 4: Frequency and percentage difference towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to Gender

Gender	Low		Moderate		High		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Male	3	2.15	135	97.12	1	0.71	139
Female	1	0.62	160	99.37	0	0	161

From the table 4 that amid the male teachers, 0.71% of them have high level of teaching competency whereas 97.12% of them have moderate level and 2.15% of them have low level of teaching competency. Similarly, amid the female teachers, 99.37% of them have moderate level and 0.62% of them have low level of teaching competency.

Table 5: ‘t’ values towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to Gender

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D	df	t value	p-value	Remarks
Male	139	1.985	0.16	300	0.58	0.28	Not significant
Female	161	1.993	0.07				

(at 0.05 significant level the table value of ‘t’ is 1.64)

From the table 5 the calculated value (0.58) is less than the table value of ‘t’ (1.64), the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to Gender.

HYPOTHESIS 2:

There will be a significant mean score difference towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to Marital Status

Table 6: Frequency and percentage difference towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to Marital Status

Marital Status	Low		Moderate		High		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Married	2	1.22	160	98.15	1	0.61	163
Unmarried	2	1.45	135	98.54	0	0	137

From the table 6 that amid the married teachers, 0.61% of them have high level of teaching competency whereas 98.15% of them have moderate level and 1.22% of them have low level of teaching competency. Similarly, amid the unmarried teachers, 98.54% of them have moderate level and 1.45% of them have low level of teaching competency.

Table 7: ‘t’ values towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to Marital status

Marital status	Number	Mean	S.D	df	t value	p-value	Remarks
Married	163	2.70	0.50	300	0.85	0.19	Not significant
Unmarried	137	2.73	0.50				

(at 0.05 significant level the table value of ‘t’ is 1.64)

From the table 7 the calculated value (0.85) is less than the table value of ‘t’ (1.64), the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to marital status.

HYPOTHESIS 3:

There will be a significant mean score difference towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to Educational Qualification

Table 8: Frequency and percentage difference towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to Educational Qualification

Educational Qualification	Low		Moderate		High		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
PG	2	1.81	108	98.18	0	0	110
UG	2	1.05	187	98.42	1	0.52	190

From the table 8 that amid the PG qualified teachers, 98.18% of them have moderate level and 1.81% of them have low level of teaching competency. Similarly, amid the UG qualified teachers, 0.52% of them have high level, 98.42% of them have moderate level and 1.05% of them have low level of teaching competency.

Table 9: ‘t’ values towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to Educational Qualification

Educational Qualification	Number	Mean	S.D	df	t value	p-value	Remarks
PG	110	2.76	0.49	300	0.58	0.28	Not significant
UG	190	2.69	0.51				

(at 0.05 significant level the table value of ‘t’ is 1.64)

From the table 9 the calculated value (0.58) is less than the table value of ‘t’ (1.64), the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to educational qualification.

HYPOTHESIS 4:

There will be a significant mean score difference towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to Type of management

Table 10: Mean score difference towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to Type of management

Type of Management	Number	Mean	S.D
Government	98	1.98	0.17
Government Aided	111	1.99	0.09
Private	91	1.98	0.10

From the table 10 the mean value of Government school teachers is 1.98 whereas the mean value of Government Aided school teachers is 1.99 and the mean value of Private teachers is 1.98. The result inferred that the Government aided school teachers value is high compare to others.

Table 11: 'F' value towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to Type of management

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.000	2	.000	.006	Not Significant
Within Groups	4.970	297	.017		

From the table 11, it is concluded that the calculated value of "F" (0.006) is less than the table value of "F" (0.05) which holds 3.04, the Null hypothesis is accepted .It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to Type of management.

HYPOTHESIS 5:

There will be a significant mean score difference towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to Teaching Experience

Table 12: Mean score difference towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to Teaching Experience

Teaching Experience	Number	Mean	S.D
0-5 years	99	1.98	0.10
5 – 10 years	129	1.98	0.12
Above 10 years	72	2.00	0.16

From the table 12 the mean value of teaching experience below 5 years is 1.98 whereas the mean value of teaching experience between '5 to 10 years' is 1.98 and the mean value of teaching experience 'Above 10 years' is 2.00. The result inferred that the mean value of teaching experience 'Above 10 years' is high compare to others.

Table 13: 'F' value towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to Teaching Experience

Teaching Experience	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.011	2	.006	.333	Not Significant
Within Groups	4.959	297	.017		

From the table 13, it is concluded that the calculated value of “F” (0.333) is less than the table value of “F” (0.05) which holds 3.04, the Null hypothesis is accepted .It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to teaching experience.

3. Conclusion

From the findings of the study conducted, it has been revealed that

- 1) There is no significant difference towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to Gender.
- 2) There is no significant difference towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to marital status.
- 3) There is no significant difference towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to educational qualification.
- 4) There is no significant difference towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to Type of management.
- 5) There is no significant difference towards teaching competency among secondary school teachers with respect to teaching experience.

The collaboration among the educators and the favorable environmental conditions of the schools completely leads to worthy teaching competency among teachers.

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